

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE METHYL METHACRYLATE HARDENED HYBRID POPLAR WOOD

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Abstract

An evaluated method based on Data envelopment analysis (DEA) to a second order conic robust counterpart was developed and used to protect the perturbation of the output within an uncertainty environment. This robust DEA was then evaluated by studying the effect of the wood hardening treatment on the hybrid poplar clones. The numerical results indicated that the performance of the methyl methacrylate (MMA) hardened hybrid poplar woods varied among clones. The reliability also suggested that the optimization of hardening treatment could be done by selecting hybrid poplar clone types and the amount of impregnated chemicals in the future experiments.

1 Introduction

Hybrid poplar is one of the most widely planted tree species in North America because of their fast growth rate and easy hybridization. They are across between North American cottonwoods, aspens, and European poplars and were primarily planted as windbreaks in many countries. Due to the native properties of the hybrid poplar (low density, high moisture content, low extractive content, and low strength), its solid wood has little commercial value. Therefore, it is primarily used as fiber source for pulp and paper industry and some engineered wood products including oriented strand board, laminated veneer lumber, and structural composite lumber.

To generate the high values of the hybrid poplar wood, wood hardening technology through methyl methacrylate (MMA) impregnation has been employed. After hardening, wood density, dimensional stability, surface properties, and mechanical properties were greatly improved [1-3]. These improved properties made poplar woods appeared to be good possible alternatives to other commercial high-grade hardwood species. However, these properties were found to be varying among different hybrid clones after treatment. Therefore, from an economic viewpoint, the optimization of this hardening treatment is necessary for industrial practice. The hybrid poplar clone type and the amount of impregnated chemicals were considered as two primary input parameters.

CCR model, the most basic model of Data envelopment analysis (DEA), was employed in this optimization process. It is an essential approach to estimate and rank the efficiencies of different Decision-Making Units (DMUs). DEA models are used in many different areas, such as finance, environment, and energy [4-6]. However, sometimes the parameters of the model, i.e. the input X_j and output Y_j , are random vectors that are not easy to control or predict and this may lead to unrealistic results. Due to these uncertainties, the robustness of the solution from the DEA structure needs to be considered. Cooper et al. presented interval DEA to cope with imprecise data and to analyze the telecommunications enterprise in South Korea [7]. Shokouhi et al. utilized Monte-Carlo simulation to

analyze the DEA with imprecise data [8]. Although it is convenient to compute the robust models because of their linear property, these robust models are too conservative to cope with extreme cases in real life [9]. Moreover, with the development of convexity in theory and improvement in practice, some conic programs are more suitable for the estimation of the robustness of parameters. Instead of using the linear robust counterpart, we formulate a classic DEA model, i.e. CCR under uncertain output within an ellipsoid ball as a second order conic program (SOCP), and evaluate the performance of MMA-hardening treated Canadian hybrid poplar woods as an initial exploration in this work.

2 Robust DEA Model

Assume there are m inputs and n outputs, then for any output θ_p , $\forall p = 1, \dots, n$, CCR model is

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \theta_p = \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rp} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ip} = 1 \\ & - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij} + \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rj} \leq 0, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n \\ & u_r \geq 0, v_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, m, \forall r = 1, \dots, s \end{aligned}$$

For robust DEA model, assume the output y_j lies in an ellipsoidal uncertainty set such as shown in the Fig. 1:

$$y_j \in U(\bar{y}_j)_\delta = \{y_j: (y_j - \bar{y}_j)^T \Theta (y_j - \bar{y}_j) \leq \delta^2\}$$

Where Θ is diagonal matrix with the variance of y_j , δ measure the deviation away from central value \bar{y}_j . Then we can formulate the Robust CCR as follows:

max t

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{r=1}^s u_r \bar{y}_{rp} - \sqrt{\sum_{r=1}^s \Theta_s u_s^2} \geq t \\ & \sum_{i=1}^m v_i \bar{x}_{ip} = 1 \\ & - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i \bar{x}_{ij} + \sum_{r=1}^s u_r \bar{y}_{rj} + \sqrt{\sum_{r=1}^s \Theta_s u_s^2} \leq 0, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n \\ & u_r \geq 0, v_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, m, \forall r = 1, \dots, s \end{aligned}$$

Ellipsoidal Uncertainty Set

3 Experiments and Methods

3.1 Experiments

25 hybrid poplar trees were chosen randomly from a 6-year-old experimental plantation near Montreal, Quebec, Canada (Table 1). The specimens extracted from those trees were impregnated with methyl methacrylate (MMA) monomer mixed with 0.5 wt.% of Vazo 52 in an autoclave and then cured by catalyst-thermal treatment. After treatment, oven-dry density, static bending and compressive properties, Janka hardness, and dimensional stability were measured, according to respective ASTM standard tests [1-3].

Table 1 General information on hybrid poplar clones

Clone	Species cross	Sample No.
1	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	1-4
2	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	5-9
3	<i>P.nigra</i> × <i>maximowiczii</i>	10-13
4	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	14-17
5	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	18-21
6	<i>P.deltooides</i> × <i>nigra</i>	22-25

3.2 Computational methods

Different properties of 25 samples before and after different experiments were recorded. Previous studies showed that clone and density difference (density after treatment – density before treatment) had significant effects on the performance of the

final specimens [1-3]. And wood density greatly accounted for the difference in mechanical properties and dimensional stability between the wood species types [1, 10]. Therefore, the density (before treatment) and density difference were used as inputs to represent the clone type and treatment factors. In addition, there is a reverse relation between density (before treatment) and density difference [11].

Table 2 Input and Output parameters for DEA model

Input 1	Density (kg/m ³) before treatment
Input 2	Density difference (kg/m ³)
Output 1	MOE difference (GPa), Bending
Output 2	MOR difference (MPa), Bending
Output 3	MCS difference (MPa), C
Output 4	MOE difference (MPa), C
Output 5	MOE difference (GPa), C⊥
Output 6	Hardness difference (N)
Output 7	Vco difference after 720 hours (%)
Output 8	D difference after 720 hours (%)

Note: difference: properties (treated – before treatment); MOE: modulus of elasticity, MOR: modulus of rupture, MCS: maximum crushing strength; Vco: Volume swelling coefficient; D: Water uptake; C||: Compression parallel to grain; C⊥: Compression perpendicular to grain.

The samples were grouped according to the clone factor (see Table 1) and the performance of these clones was evaluated. The CCR and developed robust CCR models were employed. The input and output of the models are described as follows and the data details are shown in the Table 5. Input 1 and Input 2 have a reversed relation. Since the optimization is to maximize the values of Output 1–6 and minimize the values of Output 7 and 8, reversed sign were assigned to Output 7 and 8 during the analysis.

4 Results and Discussion

The basic statistic information about the samples is summarized in Table 3. It can be seen from the third column that the stabilities are different for different properties and some properties (i.e. properties 1, 2, 4) violate far away from the first center moment, this may result in unstable performance. To eliminate this uncertainty, the output observations were

allowed to perturb within a certain ellipsoid. For instance, we allowed all properties to perturb 5%, 15% of first center moment respectively, or different properties to perturb with different range, e.g., [.20; .10; .05; .20; .10; 0; 0; 0].

Table 3 Statistical summary on the output properties

Property	Mean	Standard deviation (STD)	STD/ Mean
Output 1	0.4016	0.531	1.3222
Output 2	6.7866	6.3509	0.9358
Output 3	9.6033	4.4350	0.4618
Output 4	0.4798	0.6021	1.2547
Output 5	0.4976	0.3885	0.7806
Output 6	3524.733	947.235	0.2687
Output 7	3.3704	1.3198	0.3916
Output 8	186.2532	28.3363	0.1521

The comparison results under different conditions are shown in Table 4. According to DEA, a DMU is CCR-efficient if the score of the DMU equals to 1. If the efficient DMUs share the same clone with high probability, then it implies the treatment has the most significant influence on the corresponding clone. However, it is noted that, for a specific hybrid poplar clone, the most efficient treatment was not necessarily relevant to the highest values of the investigated properties of the specified sample, but to the higher mean value of the group with the same properties. From Table 4, it is clear that the score of sample 22–25 which represented the Clone 6 has the smallest values in all computations. This indicates the MMA hardening treatment had the least influence on the clone 6, despite its treated samples showed medium to high physico-mechanical properties.

Extreme output may affect the result significantly. For example, it seems that sample 5–9 (Clone 2) was efficient in the CCR model. However, all efficient DMUs decreased dramatically from 1 compared with other clones such as Clone 5. It indicates that the hardening treatment effects were not consistent among the investigated properties for Clone 2. One explanation is that treatment effect and clone effect (anatomical structure) may both take place. In certain properties, one effect is likely to be more dominant than the other. On the contrary, the scores related to Clone 3 still kept efficient or higher

values in robust CCR, which suggests that treatment had consistent influence in all investigated properties for Clone 3. This is most probably due to the better interaction between wood cell structure and PMMA polymer.

The average scores of these samples for each clone were calculated based on Table 4 and it was concluded that the suitability of those 6 clones for MMA hardening treatment is in an order as follows:

Clone 3 > Clone 2 ≥ Clone 4 > Clone 1 ≥ Clone 5 > Clone 6 (without robust)

Clone 3 > Clone 5 ≥ Clone 2 > Clone 4 ≥ Clone 1 > Clone 6 (with robust)

The decision for optimization of MMA treatment can be made based on this order for further research. One may choose Clone 3 instead of Clone 6 for MMA hardening treatment for industrial practice. Similarly, one may expect that less impregnated MMA in Clone 6 may result in better performance and less economic cost. Then a more efficient performance of Clone 6 can be achieved in the evaluation system. This sensitivity analysis provided another interesting insight for us in the future.

5 Conclusions

A robust DEA model was presented to protect the uncertain outputs within an ellipsoid ball and applied to evaluate the performance of MMA hardening treated hybrid poplars. The average score of each clone and an order of the selected clones in MMA hardening treatments were obtained based on the treatment efficiency. These results gave us an insight for improved experiment design in the future and an optimal outcome can be achieved provided with careful selection hybrid poplar clones and economic amount of chemicals used.

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Table 4 Numerical results by CCR models

Clone	DMU	CCR		Robust CCR (5% perturbation)		Robust CCR (15% perturbation)		Robust CCR (perturbation individually)	
		Score	average	Score	average	Score	average	Score	average
Clone 1	Sample 1	0.8858	0.9687	0.8570	0.9446	0.8098	0.9050	0.8830	0.9566
	Sample 2	1		0.9755		0.9333		1	
	Sample 3	1		0.9850		0.9579		1	
	Sample 4	0.9891		0.9608		0.9190		0.9436	
Clone 2	Sample 5	1	0.9794	0.9789	0.9550	0.9420	0.9125	1	0.9648
	Sample 6	1		0.9817		0.9489		0.9925	
	Sample 7	1		0.9767		0.9364		0.9783	
	Sample 8	0.9111		0.8870		0.8399		0.8776	
	Sample 9	0.9861		0.9507		0.8953		0.9757	
Clone 3	Sample 10	1	1.0000	0.9779	0.9820	0.9395	0.9510	0.9843	0.9961
	Sample 11	1		0.9786		0.9411		1	
	Sample 12	1		0.9714		0.9237		1	
	Sample 13	1		1.0000		1.0000		1	
Clone 4	Sample 14	1	0.9777	0.9727	0.9567	0.9272	0.9222	0.9987	0.9565
	Sample 15	0.9108		0.8779		0.8290		0.8273	
	Sample 16	1		0.9901		0.9722		1	
	Sample 17	1		0.9860		0.9606		1	
Clone 5	Sample 18	1	0.9675	0.9810	0.9419	0.9476	0.8985	1	0.9670
	Sample 19	1		0.9758		0.9345		1	
	Sample 20	1		0.9700		0.9207		0.9980	
	Sample 21	0.8698		0.8410		0.7913		0.8698	
Clone 6	Sample 22	0.6578	0.7710	0.6358	0.7438	0.5986	0.6943	0.6561	0.7684
	Sample 23	0.7772		0.7542		0.7151		0.7690	
	Sample 24	0.7424		0.7176		0.6718		0.7424	
	Sample 25	0.9064		0.8676		0.7916		0.9059	

Note: the distribution of the perturbation of last two columns, i.e., [$\pm 20\%$; $\pm 10\%$; $\pm 5\%$; $\pm 20\%$; $\pm 10\%$; 0; 0; 0] was followed by the risk perspective of RISK/RETURN.

Table 5 Data details used for CCR models

DMU	Input		Output							
	Input 1	Input 2	Static Bending		Compression parallel to grain		Compression perpendicular to grain	Compression test	Dimensional stability	
	Density before treatment (kg/m ³)	Density difference (kg/m ³)	MOE difference (GPa)	MOR difference (MPa)	Ultimate strength difference (MPa)	MOE difference (MPa)	MOE difference (GPa)	Hardness difference (N)	Volume swelling Coef. difference after 720 hours (%)	Water uptake difference after 720 hours (%)
Sample 1	-286.9749	395.3962	0.385	3.725	6.1906	0.442355	-0.02334	3292.557	2.733876	209.3475
Sample 2	-281.4945	365.7016	-0.065	2.545	3.29835	-0.18304	0.840601	3528.947	3.624272	218.1585
Sample 3	-338.6183	359.7013	0.795	13.735	10.7447	1.206007	0.478728	4260.798	3.449825	174.1365
Sample 4	-299.8840	370.0654	-0.39	-3.14	10.7447	1.206007	0.501588	2774.232	3.449636	180.1744
Sample 5	-296.2000	356.9762	0.305	1.83	12.2003	-0.4961	1.235925	4422.462	2.734641	176.9762
Sample 6	-291.6459	358.2302	0.26	15.325	17.64035	1.272828	0.374658	3355.186	2.807877	185.3676
Sample 7	-360.1941	386.2417	0.665	9.43	17.99025	0.067725	1.175509	3145.451	1.454111	140.1071
Sample 8	-323.6012	373.0435	0.195	-5.87	12.62915	0.949313	0.628084	3464.62	2.549354	169.2481
Sample 9	-325.5597	363.8611	0.51	11.57	12.04973	0.676819	0.266076	3373.166	3.523986	151.9305
Sample 10	-342.8691	368.1199	0.185	5.295	18.276	1.529431	0.259937	2770.571	2.963756	135.3446
Sample 11	-371.3568	372.5289	-0.205	14.035	3.0781	-0.18866	-0.02987	2748.33	3.231292	139.3959
Sample 12	-327.9513	344.7332	-0.705	5.065	3.1244	-0.00985	0.395313	4027.781	2.757709	165.0589
Sample 13	-326.4083	339.4178	1.89	10.625	3.58915	0.070004	-0.00084	2711.898	3.567841	167.5602
Sample 14	-273.7833	324.632	-0.2	2.805	9.91275	0.814005	-0.07537	2496.012	2.876817	192.2701
Sample 15	-276.0064	368.8988	0.23	6.135	9.33745	0.838335	0.84164	2033.588	2.452522	179.9049
Sample 16	-291.3944	303.3179	1.195	11.14	8.8381	0.013037	0.896956	2587.388	2.008413	196.9398
Sample 17	-271.0250	319.7116	0.82	3.79	10.17995	0.528654	1.122339	2652.515	2.555726	198.9914
Sample 18	-320.5229	486.6872	0.955	19.605	13.25475	1.059408	0.30697	4958.068	6.372982	212.5771
Sample 19	-298.9381	523.6213	0.64	14.035	8.2525	1.327471	0.432552	6098.597	6.283989	241.7411
Sample 20	-314.9154	462.0409	0.715	8.395	8.9521	0.295617	0.651211	3788.807	5.749593	212.1615
Sample 21	-296.8105	524.6611	0.535	11.72	7.135	0.354101	0.372067	4204.837	5.390032	228.2587
Sample 22	-327.2167	530.0345	0.285	-2.86	7.4778	0.253261	0.456802	4013.631	1.297187	180.4531
Sample 23	-298.6501	506.0479	0.51	6.74	12.3912	0.761192	-0.107	2846.933	4.015847	208.844
Sample 24	-296.1663	487.3708	0.16	0.14	4.19485	-0.33246	0.772955	3471.721	3.126148	217.8661
Sample 25	-325.6634	455.9922	0.37	3.85	8.6014	-0.45952	0.667186	5090.24	3.282902	173.5154

